

15, St Johns Street.
OXFORD.
13/2/72.

Dear David Philips,

Since I have not heard from you, and because of possible postal problems I take the liberty of summarizing my letter to you of 27 December:

" Thank you for your clarity over the question of salary. I was I must admit to some extent misled by the correspondence with Innes During Caspers. I very much believe however that it would be worthwhile to try to get your Museum at Dubai moving. I would like to come to the U.A.E. in any case from the early autumn of 1972 to look for archaeological material..... What I would propose is that I work for your Museum, but on the understanding that I would not be expected to be in Dubai full time, but could use Museum resources (vehicle) to investigate the archaeological material in the area, donating any finds to the Museum, and if political conditions permit make short trips to Iran (at my own cost)..... I do not know whether a contract would be acceptable to you on these sort of terms. Under these sort of terms in addition ~~for~~ to any income from you I could retain at least part of my present emolument for carrying out research on the Gulf.

I would also consider it essential to have a reasonable allocation of funds for strictly Museum purposes, so that exhibitions could be organized which would capture the interest of the ruler and public enough to justify the more permanent funding of the Museum at a later date".

I understand that you might be in England later this month. I would be very glad to have the opportunity of meeting of meeting t en, if that is at all possible and whatever your conclusions about the Museum.

Yours sincerely

Andrew Williamson.